

QUEERLY SAID: A LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF GENDER EXPRESSION VARIATIONS
IN QUEER THAI-TO-JAPANESE TRANSLATED MEDIA

by

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Abstract

The Thai and Japanese languages allow speakers to express their gender and sexuality linguistically. Speakers can either conform to the binary language rules of masculinity and femininity or use a nonbinary combination of rules that best express their individual identity. However, while both languages are gendered, Thai has greater flexibility in its gendering, which is especially evident when translating media from one language to another. Because Thai and Japanese both have similar gender markers, yet the latter is less flexible, linguistic gender expression from Thai to Japanese is often altered to best adapt Thai gender ideologies and expectations to Japanese ones. To investigate the differences in linguistic gender expressions, I will be analyzing fictional Thai dialogue that has been translated into Japanese. More specifically, I will be looking at queer television dramas which have gained significant popularity in Japan amongst teenagers and young adults, prompting an effort from fans to unofficially translate and provide subtitles for these shows. I argue that fan translations are an example of the morphing of Thai and Japanese language practices and are adapted to conform to the binary cis-heteronormative ideologies found in the Japanese language, often altering the dynamics and portrayals of the characters' identities.

Keywords: Thai, Japanese, gender and sexuality in language, queer media, boys' love, translation studies, intercultural communication, glocalization, media studies, queer linguistics, fan translation

Linguistic Gender Expression in Japanese and Thai

In her book *Queer Japanese: Gender and Sexual Identities through Linguistic Practices*, a detailed investigation of the linguistic practices of LGBT+ Japanese native speakers, Hideko Abe states that “speakers use linguistic resources available to them to negotiate their identity in various manners” (Abe, 2010, p. 9). This is particularly true for Japanese and Thai, which have specific gender markers such as gendered first and second-person pronouns that allow speakers to portray, or index, their gender identity in a specific way, either by conforming to the binary language rules of masculinity and femininity or by using a nonbinary combination of rules that best express their individual identity. However, while both languages are indeed gendered, Thai generally allows for greater flexibility in its gendering. Speakers of Thai can use a wider variety of personal pronouns without the indexicality of their gender identity changing much. In contrast, Japanese speakers must use a specific set of markers to maintain the same indexicality.

First and second-person pronouns in Japanese and Thai can be thought of as being on a gendered spectrum, with masculine at one end, feminine at the other, and gender-neutral in the middle. However, to accurately capture a more comprehensive pragmatic significance of pronouns in both languages, an extra axis must be included to account for politeness. This is because, apart from gender, both Thai and Japanese personal pronouns carry formal (or informal) connotations. Both languages offer speakers pronouns that must be used in formal contexts, as well as pronouns that can be used in informal contexts that call for some reservations, informal contexts where politeness is not much needed, or hostile situations that call for vulgar language.

Fig. 1, *Japanese and Thai first-person pronouns commonly found in modern media.*

While the most informal first-person pronouns for Japanese are strictly gendered (in the sense that they index a specific, binary gender expression of either strictly masculine or strictly feminine), the more informal pronouns in Thai are nearly gender-neutral, with formality being a more significant influence than gender. In contrast, most pronouns in Japanese, regardless of formality, carry a gendered connotation. This is especially true when comparing Thai and Japanese second-person pronouns. Typically, all modern Thai second-person pronouns can be used by any speaker regardless of gender and instead account more for the politeness and intimacy of the situation, though it should be noted that there are indeed trends where women typically use certain pronouns at a higher frequency than men, and vice versa.

Fig. 2, *Japanese and Thai second-person pronouns commonly found in modern media.*

It is important to understand that, as with any other language, guidelines for using gender markers in Thai and Japanese are never immutable, and actual native speakers can and do negotiate their meanings in real-life conversations, mixing and matching markers as needed. Although the graphs above are helpful for the purpose of illustrating the different varieties of pronouns that exist in Japanese and Thai, their actual categorization as "feminine, masculine, and neutral [is] negotiable...depending on the speaker's need in a given context... and require conscious intentions and strategies" (Abe, 2010, p. 145).

Interestingly, it is often fictional conversations that are the most semantically strict and do not reflect the actual fluidity and flexibility of native speakers, instead designed to serve as guidelines for native and non-native speakers when forming and indexing their identities in real conversations (Ehrlich & Nakamura, 2014, p. 384). Indeed, "We have the knowledge of how a particular group uses language, even if no group embodying that association actually exists, because we often acquire the knowledge from fictional conversations in the media" (p. 384). Media, and the language found in it, can indeed promote a sociopolitical agenda, particularly popular media aimed at young adults.

The Global Distribution of Queer Asian Media

With modern technology, global communication has rapidly evolved in the past few decades since the invention of early entertainment technology such as radio and television. Streaming platforms such as Youtube, Netflix, and Hulu, amongst others, have granted viewers access to digital media from all over the world on demand. Moreover, despite Hollywood's long reign over the entertainment media, non-English media has seen an increase in international viewership, with streaming platforms providing subtitles for their hosted content as bridges

between foreign media and local audiences. Most prominent in this rise of non-English media is the Asian entertainment industry, with East and Southeast Asian content gaining popularity beyond the continent and into the Western sphere.

Within Asian media, Boys' Love has become one of the most prominent genres in this race for global distribution. The genre commonly known as 'BL' was created in 1970s Japan, when the emergence of fan fiction in *shoujo* (girl's) media created a shift in the "conceptualization of love" as female authors began writing homoerotic romances between male characters as opposed to heterosexual romance stories (Saito, 2011, p. 174). Although Japanese BL was initially confined to print media, the 90s saw a commercialization of the genre that shifted it into the televised world with animated adaptations. Furthermore, with the help of amateur translators, BL spread outside of Japan. For almost two decades, Japan dominated the BL industry and the entertainment industry in Asia, with anime and manga becoming increasingly popular among young audiences. However, starting in the 2010s, other Asian countries began producing their own BL media, first releasing it in print, then adapting it into live-action television shows. Presently, Thailand dominates this industry, producing the most live-action BL dramas per year out of any country in the world.

On a global scale, Thailand is the biggest producer of BL dramas, with GMMTV, a television production studio and talent agency, dominating the industry in the amount and popularity of its productions. As of 2023, the company has produced over 30 BL dramas since 2016, including the country's most watched BL, *2gether The Series*, and two of the top 3 best-rated BL dramas, *Bad Buddy* and *Not Me*, on IMDb. As of August 2020, *2gether* had surpassed 100 million views on the Asian streaming platform LINE TV, making it the app's most-viewed series of all time (LINE TODAY, 2020). Additionally, as of May 2023, the series'

first episode had garnered over 34 million views on YouTube, the most popular international streaming platform for Thai BLs. In terms of ratings, *Bad Buddy* and *Not Me* are two of the only three Thai BLs with a rating of 8.8/10 on IMDb, ranking them within the top 20 best-rated television shows from Thailand; the only other BL drama to rank this high is *I Told Sunset About You*, produced by now-defunct production company Nadao Bangkok in 2020.

In November of 2022, GMMTV's Chief Executive Officer Sataporn Panichraksapong announced during the company's annual project reveal event that they have the most nominations for content and artist amongst all content producers in Thailand. GMMTV has a total of 29 nominations across various international Asian award shows, including Content Asian Awards, Asian Academy Creative Awards, and Asian Television Awards. Additionally, the company has won Best LGBTQ+ Programme Made in Asia from Content Asia Awards two years in a row (*A Tale of Thousand Stars* winning in 2021 and *Bad Buddy* winning in 2022), as well as winning the Special Award for Foreign Drama from the International Drama Festival in Tokyo also two years in a row (with *2gether The Series* winning in 2021 and *A Tale of Thousand Stars* winning in 2022), making the company's BLs the most awarded BL dramas in the industry at an international level.

Thai Boys' Love Media in Japan and the Phenomenon of the "Thai Swamp"

The popularity of BL at an international level is, arguably, due to its accessibility outside of its native sphere. Indeed, Thai BL was able to surpass Japan, the creator of the genre, and dominate the industry partly because of the globalization efforts of Thai producers, which starkly contrast with the approach of Japanese entertainment producers, notorious for blocking access to

their media outside of Japan. Particularly for GMMTV, all of their series are available to watch for free on YouTube. Additionally, the production studio releases all episodes with English subtitles and incorporates fan-translated subtitles in various other languages. This practice of reciprocal cooperation between studios and fans is essential to understanding the globalization of Asian BL; production studios such as GMMTV grant easy and free access to their content, releasing their series on widely available platforms and providing English subtitles for every episode so that international audiences can enjoy their media at the same time as local audiences. This deliberate marketing towards international fans encourages loyalty and dedication from viewers, who in turn voluntarily translate the content they consume into their native languages in hopes of increasing the popularity of the series, providing the production studio with free labor and free marketing that is beneficial for the studio itself at a local level.

The emergence of Thai BL fans in Japan presents a fascinating by-product of the global distribution of the genre. BL media was invented in Japan in the 1970s, exported to Thailand when it was commercialized in the 1990s, then finally innovated by Thailand for television and imported back into Japan in the 2010s. Thailand's adoption of BL media fits into the scholarly definition of 'glocalization': "a blend of globalisation and localisation [that describes] the way in which practices that spread across the globe will be 'nativised' by local cultures" (Robertson, 1995 as cited in Seargeant, 2012, p. 179). Furthermore, phenomena like Thai BL's popularity in Japan demonstrate that globalization works as "a two-way street" (Seargeant, 2012, p. 179) where both the culture exporting and the culture importing a practice benefit from the exchange. Thai BL media could not exist and enjoy its global fame today without Japan having invented it first, and Japanese fans could not enjoy Thai BL without Thailand having innovated the genre for television.

Beyond their reign over BL dramas in their native Thailand, GMMTV has enjoyed a significant influence in the Japanese market for the past three years. During the first months of the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced a large percentage of the world population into quarantine, GMMTV saw a rise in viewership of their content, with *2gether The Series* becoming the centerpiece of their fame abroad, including Japan. With the easy worldwide availability of GMMTV content on YouTube, and the effort of fan translators to subtitle BL series in Japanese, Thai BL quickly gained popularity amongst Japanese fans (Shūkan Gendai, 2022). Mainstream media then began taking note of the sudden rise of popularity, calling it the *tai-numa* (literally “Thai swamp” in Japanese), a term used to define the phenomenon of Japanese people’s fascination with Thai BL and the “beautiful” artists that have become the face of the industry (Sakaguchi, 2021).

With media producers now aware of the Thai BL’s popularity in Japan, attempts at capitalizing on the demand for the media emerged soon after the genre’s boom in the country. On November 2020, Japanese broadcasting company TV Asahi announced that it had formed a business partnership with GMMTV, stating that it hopes to work "with GMMTV to deliver fresh and stellar Thai content to the Japanese market and further unlock the great potential “Thai Style” entertainment holds." Since then, the Japanese company has officially broadcasted some of GMMTV’s most popular BL dramas on its national television channel, as well as being authorized to sell DVD sets of the series and live concert events featuring the artists. In that same 2020 release declaring its partnership with GMMTV, TV Asahi also announced that it would be organizing the “GMMTV Exhibition” in April and May of 2021, featuring behind-the-scenes content from the Thai series, including costumes worn by the actors on screen and exclusive merchandise of the first generation of GMMTV’s most popular actors. Following its success, the

two companies announced a year later that throughout 2022 and 2023, they would hold a second exhibition that tours multiple major cities in Japan, this time featuring both the first and second generation of the company's prominent artists. That same year, once travel restrictions had eased in Japan during the latter half of 2022, GMMTV announced that it would be sending its most prominent BL artists to Japan for the "GMMTV Japan Fan Fest," a concert and meet-and-greet event which was attended by over 20,000 Japanese fans. Since the success of the 2022 Fan Fest, GMMTV, in partnership with TV Asahi, has hosted numerous fan meetings (events in which fans can meet their artists in person, usually in the format of a mini-concert followed by Q&A sessions) in Tokyo and Osaka, with more announced for the remainder of 2023. Beyond these events, TV Asahi has co-produced variety show-style content with GMMTV, releasing it on their official Japan-exclusive streaming platform Telasa and GMMTV's official YouTube channel for global access.

Thai-to-Japanese Fan Translations of BL Media

Before TV Asahi began its partnership with GMMTV to officially broadcast their content, Japanese fans could access Thai BL series through GMMTV's official YouTube channel, which is available for fans worldwide outside of Thailand. Through the efforts of volunteer fan translators, Japanese subtitles were provided for most series before they became available through national television channels and professionally subtitled by TV Asahi. The crowd-sourced "unofficial" subtitles are featured exclusively on YouTube, where the website's interface allows for videos to have subtitles in multiple languages. GMMTV, like other drama studios that host their content on YouTube, accepts and incorporates subtitles created by fan groups or individuals who voluntarily submit translations to the company without monetary

compensation into their videos. Beyond the extraordinary business benefits that the Thai-Japan BL exchange creates for the BL industry, the attempts at translating Thai media for Japanese contexts provide a valuable and fascinating insight into the intercultural communication that comes with the globalization of digital media, particularly queer media.

Analyzing one of Thailand's very first BL dramas, *Lovesick The Series*, Baudinette (2019) writes that "Series *wai* (the Thai name for BL dramas that stems from the Japanese term *yaoi*) hybridize Thai understandings of sex and gender with explicitly Japanese models of reading same-sex attraction to create a 'glocalized' code that is becoming increasingly influential... [They] represent a domesticated form of BL media that has been adapted to the Thai mediascape" (p. 116). Indeed, although Thai BL is a direct descendant of Japanese BL, it demonstrates a nativized variant of BL media that adopts characteristics from *lakhons* (Thai soap operas) and Japanese BL so that it "possesses its own specific narrative codes" (Baudinette, 2019, p. 117) that distinguishes the genre today. In a way that is similar but converse to Baudinette's argument on the globalization of Japanese BL in Thai BL series, I argue that the Japanese subtitles featured in Thai BL series are a globalization of Thai queer language that is adapted to fit into Japanese gender ideologies reflected in the language.

Adapting Homo-social Language into Heteronormative Language

A linguistic practice common in Thai BL dramas, which often feature two male protagonists in their late teens or early twenties, is the use of the first person-pronoun *กู* (*gu*) and the second person-pronoun *เม็ง* (*meung*). This set of pronouns is common in both fictional and real conversations, and its usage is appropriate for informal situations between similarly-aged participants, particularly young male speakers (Attaviriyapap, 2015, p. 383). In BL, it conveys

a sense of equality between the two male leads who are able to express their masculinity and youth through these informal pronouns, creating a homo-social relationship in which neither character is more or less masculine than the other.

Although this set of pronouns is common practice in most Thai BLs, their Japanese translations vary from series to series, and even from episode to episode, at the translator's discretion. In my analysis of several popular Thai BLs that have been translated and subtitled by Japanese fans, I encountered several discrepancies between the linguistic gender expression of the male lead characters in Thai and Japanese. In particular, I found that translators often altered the language of one of the male characters, who are otherwise linguistically equal in the original Thai dialogue, to convey less masculinity than their fellow male character and romantic interest. Furthermore, this alteration of masculinity was only found in the characters that are assumed to take the passive feminine role in the relationship (the “bottoms”) and the masculinity of the characters that are assumed to take the active masculine role (the “tops”) had their masculinity appropriately translated from Thai into Japanese.

In 2019, the drama *Theory of Love*, which follows the romantic journeys of four filmology students, premiered globally. The 12-episode series was the second time actors Jumpol Adulkittiporn (also known as Off) and Atthaphan Phunsawat (also known as Gun), whose critically acclaimed chemistry earned them prominent status in the BL industry locally and abroad, starred as an on-screen couple. In the series, Gun Atthaphan plays the lead character, Third, a passionate film fanatic secretly in love with his best friend Khai (played by Off Jumpol), a notorious playboy and womanizer.

As is customary between male friends, Khai and Third speak to each other using the *gu/meung* set of pronouns throughout the series. However, in the Japanese subtitles provided on

YouTube by an anonymous source, Third's first-person pronoun usage when speaking to Khai varies between two sets of male pronouns, 俺 (*ore*) and 僕 (*boku*), the latter of which is considered less masculine. Indeed, in her research on queer linguistic practices, Abe (2010) found that, especially amongst gay men, "*boku* (I)...[is considered] more feminine than *ore* (I)" and that one of her gay male interviewees "made a conscious choice to use *ore* to eliminate the feminine indexicality in his linguistic practice (with the use of *boku*) [because] *ore* brings more masculine nuances for some gay men" (p. 85). Thus, particularly in gay male environments, users of the first-person pronoun *boku* are considered less masculine than users of *ore*.

Despite the fact that Third's gender expression is linguistically equal to Khai in the original Thai dialogue, Third's Japanese subtitles index him as more feminine than Khai. With the exception of certain emotional scenes where Third angrily shouts at Khai, Third's Japanese subtitles interpret his usage of *gu* as *boku*. In contrast, Khai's Japanese subtitles interpret his usage of *gu* as *ore* throughout the series without change. Thus, taking Abe's (2010) findings that *boku* is less masculine than *ore* amongst gay men in particular, the Japanese translation for the two male lead characters interprets Third as playing the feminine role in the relationship and Khai as playing the masculine role.

It is important to note that this interpretation of Third's language, as it is with speakers who do it for themselves in real-life conversations, is an intentional choice of the translator. The fact Third's pronoun usage is not always *boku*, but rather depends on the situation demonstrates that the translator is making a conscious decision to index him as less masculine in relation to Khai. Indeed, when both Third and Khai use the polite male first-person pronoun *phom* in the original Thai dialogue, it is interpreted as *boku* in the Japanese subtitles. Given that both *phom* and *boku* are polite male pronouns, this translation is appropriate. However, when Third is

interpreted as *boku* in situations that do not require the formality of *phom*, his translation implies that he regularly avoids the hypermasculine nuances that *ore* carries, which is not a linguistic practice Third does in Thai.

A partial explanation for this phenomenon can be found when considering the physical gender expression of Third as portrayed by the actor that interprets him. Gun Atthaphan is well known for his small stature and androgynous fashion choices that reject traditional masculinity. Furthermore, part of his personal brand is the fact that he presents himself as *narak* (cute, adorable, sweet), taking advantage of his youthful and soft looks. Gun is also linguistically androgynous, electing to perform the "gender-neutral" (Attaviriyapanap, 2015, p. 374) practice of using his name as a self-referential pronoun in everyday situations where *phom*, or even *gu*, would be appropriate. Thus, in the case of Gun, using pronouns in Japanese that reject hypermasculinity, such as *boku*, would be an appropriate translation of his linguistic practices in Thai.

Gun, however, does not have the same gender expression as Third. In the series, Third behaves the same as Khai linguistically, and his physical gender expression is not much different from his partner's. Nevertheless, the anonymous translators that wrote the Japanese subtitles interpreted the two as linguistically distinct. Thus, apart from taking Gun's physical appearance and gender expression, the translators also based their decisions on the relationship dynamic of a pairing (i.e., who is the "bottom" and who is the "top") when writing Khai's and Third's Japanese subtitles.

Although not explicitly shown, Khai and Third's relationship dynamic is heavily implied and assumed to be that Khai is the top and Third is the bottom. The assignment of these roles is based on various factors that play into heteronormativity: within a pairing, the partner that is

younger, physically smaller, has softer facial features, and/or behaves more femininely, amongst other criteria, will be assigned the bottom role. Thus, when making casting decisions for a BL drama, producers will look for these characteristics in an actor to assign them either the bottom or top role. It is not surprising then that Gun, who fits all of these criteria, is typically assigned the bottom role whenever he is cast in a male-male pairing, particularly when he is paired with Off (an often occurrence due to the fan demand for their brand as an on-screen couple). However, role assignments are not always superficially obvious as it is for Off and Gun, but can be more ambiguous, especially when the two male partners are physically similar.

Another series in which I found similar linguistic decisions made by the Japanese translators is *Kiss Me Again* (2018), starring Tawan Vihokratana (Tay) as Pete and Thitiphoom Techaapaikhun (New) as Kao. This series is a prequel to the original *Kiss: The Series* (2017), a romantic comedy that tells the story of a group of university engineering students and the origins of the romantic relationships that are already established in the original 2017 series. One of the relationships explored in *Kiss Me Again* is that of Pete and Kao, two first-year students who have known each other since high school and have never gotten along (a narrative trope commonly found in BL and known as “enemies-to-lovers”). Although secondary characters to the story, Pete and Kao’s relationship was particularly popular because of the BL nature of it (i.e., because it is a romantic relationship between two men as opposed to the heterosexual relationships of the main characters) and consequently, GMMTV released a special edition of the series featuring only their scenes. On YouTube, where the special edition of the series is available to watch globally, the Japanese subtitles are provided by the TayNew Japan Fan Club, a group of Japanese fans dedicated to the support of Tay and New as an on-screen couple.

Like Khai and Third, Pete and Kao are male peers of the same age and belong to the same friend group. Accordingly, they also use the pronoun set *gu/meung* when speaking to each other in the original Thai dialogue. Furthermore, just like Khai and Third, Pete and Kao's Japanese subtitles change the gender indexicality of the character who assumes the bottom role (Kao, in this case). In contrast, in his Japanese subtitles, Pete uses *ore* to refer to himself, and Kao uses the less masculine pronoun *boku*. Interestingly, this alteration of linguistic gender expression also extends to Kao's second-person pronoun usage, with the subtitles interpreting his *meung* (you) in reference to Pete as *kimi*. *Kimi*, like *boku*, is a pronoun that is most commonly used by male speakers but, in certain contexts, does not convey the same hypermasculinity as *omae* (Abe, 2010, p. 85), the second-person pronoun that is often paired with the first-person pronoun *ore*. On the other hand, Pete's Japanese subtitles maintain his gender indexicality and interpret his *gu/meung* usage as *ore/omae*.

In contrast to Khai and Third, whose relationship dynamics are more obvious because of their physical appearance, Pete and Kao's role assignments are not as apparent. Indeed, both characters (and the actors that play them) have a similar physique, age, and gender expression, making the question of who takes the top role and who takes the bottom role harder to answer. However, viewers who watch *Kiss Me Again* with Japanese subtitles would immediately be able to perceive the characters' relationship dynamics and roles solely through Pete and Kao's pronoun usage.

This linguistic practice of assigning the bottom character *boku/kimi* pronoun usage can be found in Japanese BL media. It is particularly common for character pairings in which the top character is portrayed as a troubled student and rule breaker, and the bottom character is portrayed as a model student and rule follower. For example, the popular BL manga *Doukyuusei*

(*Classmates* in English), written by Asumiko Nakamura, featured two male main characters who fit precisely that description. Indeed their pronoun usage is as expected: the top, Kusakabe, a laidback student who prefers to play with his rock band, uses the *ore/omae* pronoun set, while the bottom, Sajou, a dedicated but shy student, uses the *boku/kimi* pronoun set. Pete and Kao are similarly characterized in their series: Kao is notably a high-achieving student who often works as a tutor to earn money to help his single working-class mother. In contrast, Pete, the only son of a wealthy family, is often arrogant and neglects his studies.

Although their physical appearances do not give any apparent indications of their assigned roles, their characterizations as “the good student who loves his mother” and “the rich arrogant son” may have given the translators an indication of who is the top and who is the bottom based on their levels of formality and how appropriately they behave in formal situations, such as addressing their parents, as is the case with Kusakabe and Sajou (the relationship between politeness and gender expression will be discussed in the following section).

Indeed, the translators who provided the Japanese subtitles for their series may very well have been basing their linguistic decisions on practices they have encountered in their local BL media, such as *Doukyuusei*. As Baudinette (2019) writes, Thai BL media is a glocalization and adaptation of Japanese BL media, combining models from Japanese BL and Thai cultural understandings of gender and sexuality. Conversely, the Japanese subtitles for *Kiss Me Again* demonstrate a glocalization of Thai gender and sexuality in BL media that takes the fluidity of Thai pronouns and adapts them into the binary heteronormative expectations found in Japanese BL. Indeed, Japanese BL often portrays queer men as reflecting “gender norms for women in social contexts, especially ideas surrounding family and marriage” (Saito, 2011, p. 173). Additionally, in traditional Japanese BL, the male character’s “sexual and domestic roles are

often constructed as masculine and feminine” (p. 184), which creates a “reappropriation of heterosexual roles” (p. 187) in homosexual settings. With these being the models of traditional Japanese BL, it is no wonder that the Japanese translators for both *Theory of Love* and *Kiss Me Again* felt that audiences would be more accustomed to male-male pairings if the top and bottom roles were more clearly established.

Heteronormative Language in Senior-Junior Queer Relationships

However, not all Thai BL stories feature two male characters who are similar in age and peers in school. An increasing number of Thai BLs feature relationships between an older male character (the senior) and a younger male character (the junior). These series pose a different linguistic scenario in Thai and Japanese, as the two languages account for politeness in conjunction with gender expression. There are several ways in which a senior and a junior can refer to themselves and each other when speaking Thai: the senior can use impolite language (i.e., *gu/meung*) while the junior uses polite language to establish a power dynamic that humbles the junior; the senior can use the kinship term พี่ (*phi*, literally “elder sibling”) as self-referential in place of pronouns to acknowledge their superiority to the junior while the junior either maintains polite language to establish a sense of familiarity; or both senior and junior can use polite language and pronouns to establish a distance between the two speakers.

One exemplary series of the last scenario mentioned above is the award-winning BL drama *A Tale of Thousand Stars* (2021) starring Pirapat Watthanasetsiri (Earth) and Sahaphap Wongratch (Mix). The 10-episode drama follows the story of Tian, the son of a wealthy family who decides to travel to the mountains in the north of Thailand and become a volunteer teacher to fulfill the wish of the owner of the heart that was transplanted into him after he underwent

emergency surgery. At the local village, Tian meets the chief forest ranger who is charged with looking after him, Phupha, a friend of the deceased owner of Tian's new heart. Shortly after their meeting the two begin a rocky relationship that turns romantic.

In the original Thai dialogue, Tian and the Chief are linguistically equal despite their age gap and different social standing within the village, using the polite masculine first-person pronoun *ผม* (*phom*) and the polite second-person pronoun *คุณ* (*khun*) when speaking to each other. However, in the Japanese subtitles, which are provided by the 1000stars Japanese Fan Club, the Chief uses the impolite masculine *ore/omae* pronoun set while Tian uses the polite masculine first-person pronoun *boku* paired with the gender-neutral polite second-person pronoun *あなた* (*anata*). Furthermore, while in Thai, neither of them uses the sentence-ending particle *ครับ* (*krab*) to make a sentence polite, in the Japanese subtitles, Tian's sentences are conjugated in the polite form while the Chief's remain in the impolite form.

This interpretation of the Chief's and Tian's language demonstrates not only the language ideologies that dictate how juniors are expected to behave toward their seniors but how politeness can be directly correlated to gender expression. In Japanese, more so than in Thai, "polite, indirect, and soft ways of speaking are established as normative ways of expressing the speaker's femininity" (Ehrlich & Nakamura, 2014, p. 378). In other words, speakers whose language is more polite than their counterparts' language in a conversation will index themselves as more feminine, or at least less masculine, than the other person. Thus, Tian's polite language combined with his pronoun set usage in the Japanese subtitles reinforces the heteronormative gender roles that Japanese BL expects of its male-male pairings.

It is important to note, however, that the submissiveness of Tian's language towards the Chief in the Japanese subtitles is exclusive to their conversations, and Tian's pronoun and

politeness usage varies when he speaks to other characters. For example, when speaking to his friend of the same age, both the friend and Tian have the *ore/omae* pronoun set as an interpretation of their usage of *gu/meung* in Thai. Then, when Tian is speaking to the younger son of the village leader, Tian uses the self-referential *phi* in place of a first-person pronoun for himself and addresses Longtae by his name, while Longtae uses the polite male first-person pronoun *phom* and refers to Tian by the kinship term *phi*. The Japanese subtitles interpret their language usage by giving Tian the softened masculine *boku/kimi* pronoun set as an attempt to adapt the familiarity of using the self-referential *phi* indexes in Thai. Furthermore, the subtitles give Longtae the same polite *boku/anata* pronoun set that Tian uses when speaking to the Chief as an interpretation of his language towards Tian, who is his senior. These two variations in Tian's Japanese subtitles demonstrate that the translators understand the nuances behind his language usage in the original Thai language that change depending on who the listener is, interpreting his language towards his friend and his junior appropriately and in a way that maintains a similar gender index from Thai. However, instead of maintaining the linguistic equality that the Chief and Tian have in Thai, the translators reinforce the linguistic inequality that is expected in both senior-junior conversations and male-male BL contexts in Japanese. These discrepancies in the characters' indexing when translating between their original dialogue and their subtitles demonstrate that factoring in politeness and gender expression poses a challenge for translators who wish to accurately interpret dialogue but are limited to the social conventions of the Japanese language.

This challenge is especially evident in the translation of one of the most famous Thai BL dramas in Japan, *SOTUS The Series* (2016). This drama, starring Thai BL pioneers Perawat Sangpotirat (Krist) and Prachaya Ruangroj (Singto), holds renowned status in Thailand and

Japan as GMMTV's very first BL, and one of the first Thai BLs that was officially distributed in Japan. Additionally, its success and the popularity of Krist and Singto's brand as an on-screen couple are widely considered to be what saved the company from bankruptcy and earned it its prominent role in the industry. *SOTUS*'s popularity in Japan is so prominent that the original Thai soft novels on which the series is based have been translated into Japanese and adapted into an illustrated manga version. Furthermore, despite Singto's departure from GMMTV in 2020 and the fact that the final season of *SOTUS* ended in 2018, marking the last time Krist and Singto played an on-screen couple in a full series, the two actors' fame in Japan remains strong, with both of them frequently traveling to Tokyo for promotional and fan events.

SOTUS follows the story of Kongpob (played by Singto), a first-year engineering student subjected to the hazing system common in Thai universities. Arthit (played by Krist), a handsome but intimidating third-year student, works as Kongpob's hazer, who, in turn, frequently challenges the senior and the hazing system that forces first-year students to unconditionally obey the third-years' orders, creating a rivalry between the two that slowly develops into romantic feelings as the story progresses.

In the original Thai dialogue, Kongpob and Arthit speak to each other similarly to Tian and the Chief, with both of them using the polite and distant pronoun set *phom/khun* to convey the formality expected during the hazing activities, as well as whenever they encounter each other outside of school. Furthermore, Kongpob uses the polite ending particle *khraab* when speaking to Arthit, as would be expected of him as the junior being hazed, to establish the power imbalance between the two. The Japanese subtitles for the series, provided by the KristSingto Japanese Fan Club, do indeed maintain this power imbalance by translating Kongpob's language into the polite form and giving him the polite first-person pronoun *boku* and referring to Arthit

by either the polite second-person pronoun *anata* or the kinship term 先輩 (*senpai*, literally “superior”). However, Arhit’s Japanese subtitles do not retain the same formality that he has in Thai, assigning him the impolite and masculine pronoun set *ore/omae* when he speaks both to the juniors he hazes and to his friends in casual conversation.

This loss in formality in Arhit’s language demonstrates the ideology in Japanese that politeness in language indexes femininity and submissiveness (Ehrlich & Nakamura, 2014). Because the power imbalance between the third-year hazers and the first-year juniors is essential to the story and relationship dynamics of the characters, the Japanese translators must compromise Arhit’s formal language in Japanese so as to not affect the indexing of his status as superior. However, this compromise, in turn, affects the portrayal of his relationship dynamic with Kongpob and the other juniors once the hazing activities end and his status changes from feared hazer to reliable mentor. In the original Thai dialogue, Arhit changes his language towards the other juniors when the hazing activities end, switching from using *phom* as a first-person pronoun to the self-referential *phi*. However, his language towards Kongpob remains the same, even during *SOTUS S* (2018), the series’ second season, in which the two are in an established romantic relationship.

That Arhit remains using *phom/khun* in conversation with Kongpob after the hazing activities and well into their relationship does not indicate a distance between the two, but rather the contrary. Indeed, both *phom* and *khun* have indexes that are very dependent on context, and the latter especially has “referential potential [that] ranges from strangers to intimates such as one’s spouse” (Attaviriyapap, 2015, p. 383). In other words, while *khun* as a second-person pronoun can be used as a polite particle (as Arhit does while he hazes the juniors), it is also common for spouses to refer to each other with this pronoun as it conveys a sense of gentleness

that comes with the politeness itself. Interestingly, this phenomenon also exists in Japanese, as the second-person pronoun *anata* can be used as both a polite pronoun between strangers and as a term of endearment between spouses. However, while *khun* “is the most [gender] neutral form among the polite second-person pronouns” (Attaviriyapap, 2015, p. 383), *anata* is more commonly used by female speakers and still carries a feminine index that corresponds to the relationship between politeness and femininity in Japanese. Thus, while the Japanese translators could have interpreted Arhit’s *khun* towards Kongpob as *anata* to maintain the formality it initially carried, as well as the intimacy it conveys once their relationship turns romantic, they compromised his formality, and later intimacy, for the sake of his status as superior.

Unfortunately, this preservation of authority affects the intimacy that comes with the *khun* usage between Arhit and Kongpob at a romantic level. The fact that his language towards the juniors changes but not towards Kongpob is essential to their relationship, so much so that there is a scene in the series where Kongpob asks Arhit why he still uses *phom/khun* with him instead of the familiar kinship term *phi*. Thus, after the hazing activities end, Arhit’s exclusive way of referring to Kongpob as *khun* becomes a way to signal his intimacy with him; their love language, in a way. However, this intimacy is not portrayed in their Japanese language because, while Arhit’s language remains the same towards Kongpob (i.e., he still uses *ore/omae*), his language towards the other juniors also remains the same. Thus, there is no distinction between the way Arhit speaks to Kongpob and the way he speaks to other juniors in Japanese, erasing a language dynamic that is significant to their romantic relationship, for the sake of preserving Arhit’s superiority (and masculinity) over the juniors.

This change in language usage and its pragmatic implications is concerning for the translation of Thai BL series because it can change how audiences perceive the characters and

their relationship. Although the subtitles provided by the KristSingto Japan Fan Club are amateur translations that were voluntarily submitted by fans, their influence on how viewers interpret the story and the characters is significant; it can encourage interpretations, and even misinterpretations, that are not present in the original Thai story, or even in other translations. *SOTUS*'s translation, in particular, demonstrates how one group's interpretation dictates how a collective of fans perceive characters.

Shortly after the publication of the Japanese translation of the *SOTUS* novel, fans of the television series noticed that the language practices of the novel's characters were almost identical to the YouTube translation, with some sentences seemingly matching the subtitles word-for-word. The similarity was so stark that the publishing house that translated and distributed the novel, Daria Series uni, later announced that they had indeed based their translation on the YouTube subtitles so as to provide a dialogue with language practices that fans of the television series version were already familiar with. Consequently, the editor had to issue a public apology to the KristSingto Japan Fan Club for using their translation without permission, and the novel was then reprinted to give translation credits to the Fan Club in the official novel.

The Political Implications of Translating Queer Language

Incidents like the Japanese translation of the *SOTUS* novel are exemplary of the influence fan translations have on how the Japanese sphere perceives BL media. Prior to the commercialization and official distribution of Thai BL in Japan, fan subtitles and translations served as the first point of contact between Thai media and Japanese audiences. Even after Thai BL was officially translated by TV Asahi and other distributors, these translations remained the

first impression fans had of the characters, dictating how viewers perceived their identities, regardless of whether or not they are accurately representative of their original characterization.

As Davies (2012) writes, “translators can and do modify the content of the source text, with a variety of consequences, and...they may choose to present the translated text as something essentially foreign or adapt it to make it more accessible for the target audience” (p.374). Indeed, the alteration of pronoun usage and, consequently, the gender expression of the characters is an adaptation of Thai understandings of gender into Japanese ideology found in BL media, which often rely on heteronormative ideologies that force queer and fluid identities into male and female boxes.

Media, in particular, often serves as guidelines for linguistic practices from which viewers can obtain linguistic and pragmatic knowledge. Thus, fictional conversations in media can be analyzed “as practices undertaken by a particular agent engaged in a particular sociopolitical process” (Ehrlich & Nakamura, 2014, p. 388). In the case of the Japanese translators, whether consciously or not, their interpretations of Thai language in queer contexts as heteronormative “promote stereotypes” (Davies, 2012, p. 384) that romance is defined as a relationship between male and female identities regardless of the actual gender of the persons involved. Because their native cultural understandings of queerness differ from those of the media they consume, Japanese translators must often glocalize the queerness of the characters themselves, even if it means erasing it partially or altogether.

Although there is legitimate linguistic and pragmatic reasoning behind the heteronormative adaptations of Thai BL into Japanese, these translations often depoliticize an industry that is becoming more and more political. For the last few years, Thai BL has served as political propaganda that has helped normalize positive queer representation in mainstream

media that was previously heavily heterosexual. Furthermore, while BL remains a niche and somewhat taboo genre in Japan, the economic influence of the BL industry in Thailand has brought (marketable and profitable) visibility to queer content, making it a popular and desirable industry for emerging artists who are seeking to quickly gain fame. Furthermore, Thai BL actors dominate local popular media as a whole; magazine covers, award shows, billboards, and television commercials for a diverse range of products and services are often headlined by artists who come from the BL industry.

Most importantly, with the rise of youth activism in Thailand following years of turbulent political activity, consumers of BL (who are often the very youth who lead political movements) expect their idols to be politically involved and well-versed (Baudinette, 2022). Indeed, many BL artists have been using their platforms to express support for progressive political causes, such as the legalization of marriage equality in Thailand, one of the most pressing political issues in the country today. Additionally, in the May 2023 general elections, which sought to remove from power General Prayut Chan-o-cha, the former military leader who became Prime Minister of Thailand after the 2014 military coup d'état, many artists and producers of BL media openly supported the progressive opposition party, the Move Forward Party, which campaigned on political reform, demilitarization, the removal of the *lèse-majesté* laws, and the legalization of same-sex marriage.

Beyond the artists who become the faces of BL, producers, directors, writers, and creators of BL media in Thailand are often openly queer and transgender individuals who deliberately incorporate political agendas into their content. Some of GMMTV's most popular series, for example, have featured conversations around coming out, marriage equality, same-sex parenting, realistic queer representation, activism, government corruption, gender equality,

mental health, disability rights, homophobia, and transphobia. For example, the critically acclaimed BL drama *Not Me* (2021), directed by trans woman Anucha Boonyawatana, had a heavily political subplot that drew direct references from real-life events such as the kidnapping and disappearance of activists, pro-gay marches, as well as antagonist characters that served as an allegory for corrupt politicians and business conglomerates; the drama even featured original art from well-known queer and activist artists. A year later in 2022, GMMTV hired nonbinary director and former Member of Parliament Tanwarin Sukkhapisit to direct *The Eclipse*, a BL series that used a high school setting as a metaphor for conservative and corrupt governments who seek to silence the progressive opposition. Furthermore, many of GMMTV's resident directors and producers are openly queer men, such as Pawis Sowsrion, Nuttapong Mongkolsawas, Tichakorn Phukhaotong, and Noppaharnach Chaiwimol, director of the two BL series which won the award for Best LGBTQ+ Programme Made in Asia from Content Asia Awards, *A Tale of Thousand Stars* (2021) and *Bad Buddy* (2022).

Conclusion

Ultimately, Japanese translations that enforce heteronormative ideologies effectively erase the queerness of an industry that is openly and politically queer and do a disservice to the efforts of artists and creators of BL that use Thai BL media to push a political agenda in support of queer rights. Furthermore, Thai BL has evolved in the past four years to abandon harmful stereotypes surrounding gender roles that were standard practice in classic Japanese BL and instead provide stories that feature positive and realistic queer representation. However, when Japanese translators enforce heteronormativity through the subtitles they provide for the series, that progress is reverted to late 20th-century Japanese BL models. Thus, in order to respectfully

adapt Thai BL media for Japanese audiences, translators must accurately translate the series in a way that preserves the linguistic queerness of their characters; and, in the process, import the political agenda that the creators of Thai BL sow into their content in the hopes of inspiring their young viewers to advocate for a better, more inclusive future.

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